

ISic1259

I.Sicily inscription 1259

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

breccia (pietra rossa di Taormina)

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico, inventory 1

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140747

1. ὁ δᾶμος τῶν Ταυρομενιτᾶν
2. Ὀλυμπιν Ὀλύμπιος Μεστὸν
3. νικάσαντα Πύθια κέλητι
4. τελείωι.
- 5.

Edition: PHI337259

1. Ὀλυμπιν Ὀλύμπιος Μεστον ²= an abbreviation (siglum) of a demotic²
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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